

RL-MINDS: Reinforcement Learning for Mobility-induced Duty-Cycles in WSN for Underground Mines

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Abstract—Underground mines increasingly depend on pillar-mounted wireless sensor networks to deliver safety-critical measurements—temperature, humidity, toxic-gas levels, and mobility cues—to miners’ mobile devices, which opportunistically relay data during encounters. However, underground environments impose severe energy constraints: battery replacement is hazardous and costly, energy harvesting is scarce, and mobile charging access is limited, leaving many areas underserved. As a result, sensors must operate with *extreme energy discipline* while maintaining timely and reliable data delivery. Existing duty-cycling and scheduling methods often rely on static policies, require manual penalty tuning, or fail to adapt to dynamic miner mobility, spatially varying channel conditions, and heterogeneous battery states. To overcome these limitations, we propose RL-MINDS, a constrained reinforcement-learning (RL) framework that formulates duty-cycle scheduling as a constrained Markov decision process (CMDP) to jointly *optimize energy consumption and net bit rate*. RL-MINDS enforces energy and battery constraints using adaptive Lagrangian multipliers updated through proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control, eliminating manual tuning and ensuring stable constraint satisfaction. Meanwhile, the RL agent selects sensor duty cycles conditioned on spatial variations in miner density, underground channel conditions, and individual battery states. An attention-augmented variational autoencoder further compresses high-dimensional network states, enabling scalable policy learning. Simulations on a realistic 100-sensor underground network show that RL-MINDS achieves a 28% higher net bit rate than the strongest baseline, utilizes 95% of the energy budget, and reduces energy-constraint violations to 1.4% at convergence.

Index Terms—Wireless sensors, duty-cycle, underground mines, proximal policy optimization, variational autoencoder.

I. INTRODUCTION

In underground mines, where environments are hazardous and conditions can change within seconds, resilient low-latency sensing is a safety imperative. Battery-powered wireless sensors continuously report gas concentrations, temperature, humidity, and miner locations to the devices carried by miners. Together, these devices form a delay- and disruption-tolerant network (DTN) [1] within the mine. Replacing depleted sensor batteries is costly and hazardous [2] due to difficult terrain, while practical energy-harvesting options are scarce and wireless chargers cannot reliably reach every drift. As a result, sensors must allocate their limited energy judiciously [3]. A common control mechanism is a sensor’s *duty*

cycle—the fraction of time its sensing and radio subsystems remain active—which in mines depends on miners’ movement patterns and their interaction with these devices. Because miner mobility and the mine’s geometry produce rapid fluctuations in workload and channel quality, dynamically adapting duty cycles to these conditions is critical to maintain reliable, energy-efficient sensing in such harsh environments.

Model-free reinforcement learning (RL) is well-suited to sequential decision-making tasks in non-stationary settings such as underground mines, where miner traffic, channel fading, and occasional evacuation congestion dynamically alter network conditions. By conditioning per-slot duty-cycle decisions on current observations, RL can improve energy efficiency and extend sensor lifetime while meeting real-time sensing requirements [4]. Prior work has applied RL to energy management in various resource-constrained domains, but *RL-based duty-cycle control that explicitly addresses the unique dynamics of non-stationary underground environments* remains largely unexplored [3]. Deployment in environments such as underground mines must balance throughput and network lifetime under strict operational limits. Therefore, the controller must be constraint-aware and coordinated, rather than purely reward-driven or reactive on a per-node basis. However, standard RL maximizes cumulative reward without explicit constraint enforcement, risking energy budget violations or catastrophic battery depletion—unacceptable in safety-critical underground environments where sensor failures can delay emergency response. This motivates formulating duty-cycle scheduling as a *constrained* RL problem, where energy and battery limits are explicitly modeled as constraints in a constrained Markov decision process (CMDP). Instead of relying on manually tuned penalty terms, these constraints are enforced through proportional-integral-derivative (PID)-controlled Lagrangian relaxation, which automatically learns appropriate dual weights during training [5].

Many prior approaches focus on optimizing energy consumption at the individual-node level, with less attention given to policies that *jointly schedule the activity patterns of multiple sensors* under a single controller [6]. We refer to this latter regime as *system-level control*: a single policy assigns duty cycles to all sensors jointly, in contrast to per-sensor agents acting independently. System-level control leverage global channel observations to dynamically adjust duty-cycle durations and enable adaptive coverage expansion during localized

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emergencies during accidents/disasters. Additionally, placing a separate deep RL (DRL) agent *per sensor* is impractical in mines; it is computationally inefficient, creates high maintenance overhead, and prevents coordinated behavior, producing suboptimal system performance as sensor counts scale (e.g., tens to hundreds of nodes) [7]–[9]. Edge resources inside mines are limited, and most heavy training/inference must run on a server in a shielded control or surface station.

Furthermore, actor–critic algorithms such as proximal policy optimization (PPO) are generally better suited for high-dimensional and continuous control tasks compared to value-based methods like deep Q-networks (DQN). However, their effectiveness critically depends on how well the observed state captures consistent and informative dynamics. In large-scale and dynamic environments such as wireless sensor networks (WSNs) in underground mining, raw sensor features often exhibit high variance due to miner mobility and channel-power fluctuations. This motivates learning a *compact representation that stabilizes policy optimization and accelerates convergence*. Although such representation learning underpins stable continuous control, existing RL studies in underground mining have largely focused on energy consumption prediction, with little emphasis on active WSN control. For instance, [10] used a PPO–LSTM model to predict sensor battery depletion, *without any control over the WSN battery*, based on miner mobility patterns, primarily to support maintenance planning.

Nevertheless, there are two practical challenges that govern performance in underground WSNs. First, the joint state–action space grows exponentially with the number of observed features; as the feature dimension D increases, tabular methods quickly become intractable [11]. Second, raw observations are structured and noisy; neighboring sensors exhibit correlated channel conditions and miner densities, while battery levels and connectivity evolve temporally. Recent work shows that explicitly learning a compact latent state via state representation learning (SRL) substantially improves sample efficiency, robustness, and policy transferability in RL [12], [13]. In particular, variational autoencoders (VAEs) regularize the latent space through reconstruction and Kullback–Leibler (KL) divergence, and therefore serve as an effective denoiser for high-variance sensor inputs [14].

To address these challenges, we propose RL-MINDS, a *system-level* deep RL framework that jointly schedules duty cycles for all sensors in a large region of an underground mine. The policy is trained centrally on recorded sensor traces, and then a compact runtime model is deployed to the nearest base station to enable low-latency inference even when backbone connectivity is unreliable. Moreover, to mitigate the curse of dimensionality and stabilize continuous control, RL-MINDS integrates a VAE—whose encoder and decoder *incorporate multi-head self-attention*—into the DRL pipeline. The VAE projects high-dimensional observations onto a low-dimensional latent vector that preserves inter-feature dependencies while attenuating noise, thereby accelerating policy convergence and improving robustness. In summary, this paper makes the following contributions:

- **RL-MINDS framework:** We propose RL-MINDS, a practical PPO-based framework that formulates duty-cycle assignment as a CMDP and jointly schedules duty cycles for multiple sensors. RL-MINDS incorporates *miner-mobility patterns* and an *underground-specific wireless channel model*, enabling decisions that adapt to real-time channel variations, miners’ mobility and other dynamic mine conditions.
- **Adaptive constraint handling:** We address the CMDP via Lagrangian relaxation, using PPO to optimize the policy under a Lagrangian-augmented objective while updating dual variables through PID control—enabling automatic constraint satisfaction without manual penalty tuning.
- **System-level control & deployment:** We adopt centralized system-level control over the joint duty-cycle for all sensors, avoiding the overhead of per-node agents. Training runs on a central server, while a lightweight policy is deployed at underground mine base stations for low-latency inference.
- **Attention-enhanced representation learning:** We design a VAE with *multi-head self-attention* to compress correlated observations into compact latent states, thereby mitigating the dimensionality, preserving spatio-temporal dependencies, attenuating stochastic noise in wireless channel power, and improving both policy learning speed and robustness.
- **Performance Evaluation:** We benchmark RL-MINDS against state-of-the-art methods through extensive simulations, demonstrating a *28% higher net bit-rate (NBR)* compared to baselines and a *energy constraint violation to only 1.4%*, highlighting its superior energy efficiency and reliability under dynamic underground mine conditions.

II. RELATED WORKS

Much of the prior works using RL in energy management target *above-ground* deployments where energy sources, channel dynamics, and operational constraints differ substantially from underground mines. Early tabular approaches such as Q-learning were applied to simple configuration tasks [15], but they struggle to scale and often fail to converge in large, non-stationary environments. Some recent RL approaches use deep learning and exploit contextual information or decompose networks into subsystems to reduce learning complexity; for instance, DQN or actor-critic-based schemes have been used for subsystem-level resource allocation [9], [16]. While these contributions demonstrate the potential of RL for WSN energy management, most assume modest state–action dimensionality or independent per-node control, limiting scalability and coordinated behavior in large deployments. A recent study [10] employed a PPO–LSTM model for battery-level prediction in underground settings, focusing on energy forecasting rather than active control to design optimal duty cycles to prolong the battery life of sensing nodes.

Some energy-harvesting WSN research emphasizes lightweight learners that preserve node lifetime under very small state/action spaces (e.g., *RLMan* [17]), but such approaches do not scale well to system-level coordination across dozens of sensors. Wearable IoT studies demonstrate the applicability of PPO and other modern DRL algorithms

to device-level energy control [18], yet they seldom address the extreme channel variability, constrained infrastructure, and safety requirements of underground environments.

Underground sensor networks introduce distinct physical and operational challenges: anisotropic path loss, scarce harvestable energy sources, constrained access for maintenance and charging, and safety-critical traffic patterns that can include evacuation scenarios. Studies specific to underground or subterranean deployments identify sporadic ambient energy sources (light, thermal, radio frequency) and emphasize the importance of specialized energy-management strategies [3]. However, RL-based duty-cycle control that jointly schedules many sensors while explicitly modeling miner mobility and underground channel characteristics remains unexplored.

In summary, prior work offers valuable algorithmic building blocks (e.g., online learning, continuous-control DRL, and subsystem decomposition), but important gaps remain in scalable, coordinated, mine-aware RL solutions that (i) operate at the system level, (ii) handle high-dimensional structured observations, and (iii) enforce the strict energy and safety constraints of underground deployments without manual reward shaping. We address these gaps by formulating duty-cycle scheduling as a constrained MDP with adaptive Lagrangian penalties, and by integrating attention-enhanced representation learning into a system-level DRL controller.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The duty-cycle controller in an underground mine must balance two competing objectives: sensors must transmit frequently enough to deliver safety-critical data, yet their batteries are finite and replacement is hazardous. A controller that maximizes net bit rate alone will deplete the batteries, while one that minimizes energy alone will fail to deliver data reliably. The constrained Markov decision process (CMDP) framework separates these concerns: the primary objective NBR is maximized subject to explicit constraints on per-slot energy and minimum battery level, rather than combining all three into a single hand-tuned reward. The Lagrange multipliers introduced below act as adaptive weights that the training process tightens when constraints are violated and loosens when they are satisfied with margin, removing the need to manually search for trade-off coefficients across diverse mine conditions.

We formulate duty-cycle scheduling for underground WSNs as a CMDP [19]. A CMDP extends the standard MDP by incorporating auxiliary cost functions and constraint thresholds, thereby cleanly separating the primary objective (net bit rate maximization) from critical operational limits such as energy budgets and battery safety.

State space. At each time step t , the state aggregates six per-sensor features:

$$\mathcal{S}_t = \{(b_t^m, \zeta_t^m, k_t^m, g^m, \mu_E^m, \mu_B^m) \mid m \in \mathcal{M}\},$$

where for each sensor $m \in \mathcal{M}$, $b_t^m \in [0, 1]$ denotes the battery level, ζ_t^m is the channel power normalized by a running

maximum, k_t^m is the number of miners within communication range, and $g^m \in \{0, 1\}$ is a gravity-point indicator marking safety-critical locations (e.g., refuge chambers or shaft intersections). The signals $\mu_E^m, \mu_B^m \in [-1, 1]$ represent energy- and battery-constraint margins, respectively. The margins provide explicit constraint-awareness: the *energy margin* measures consumption relative to an equal share of the system budget,

$$\mu_E^m = \text{clip}\left(\frac{(\tau_E/M) - e_{t-1}^m}{\tau_E/M}, -1, 1\right), \quad (1)$$

where e_{t-1}^m denotes the energy consumed by sensor m in the previous slot and τ_E is the per-step energy threshold. The clipping operator bounds μ_E^m to the interval $[-1, 1]$. The *battery margin* encodes proximity to the safety threshold,

$$\mu_B^m = \text{clip}\left(\frac{b_t^m - \tau_B}{1 - \tau_B}, -1, 1\right). \quad (2)$$

where τ_B denotes the battery threshold. Positive values indicate satisfaction; negative values signal violations, enabling the policy to anticipate breaches and adjust duty cycles.

Action space. The agent outputs a system-level control vector assigning duty cycles to all sensors:

$$\mathcal{A}_t = \{a_t^m \mid m \in \mathcal{M}\}, \quad a_t^m \in [0, 0.95], \quad (3)$$

where a_t^m denotes the duty-cycle fraction (active time ratio) for sensor m as defined in [4].

Primary objective. The agent maximizes expected discounted net bit rate:

$$J(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_\pi \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t \frac{\bar{B}_r(t)}{B_{\max}} \right], \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{B}_r(t) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} B_r^m(t)$ is the mean net bit-rate across sensors and B_{\max} is the theoretical peak rate for normalization.

Constraint functions. We define normalized instantaneous violation costs corresponding to the operational limits for the *energy constraint* $C_E(s_t, a_t)$ and *battery constraint* $C_B(s_t)$ as

$$C_E(s_t, a_t) = \left[\frac{E_t - \tau_E}{\tau_E} \right]_+, \quad C_B(s_t) = \left[\frac{\tau_B - b_t^{\min}}{\tau_B} \right]_+ \quad (5)$$

The objective is to minimize expected constraint violations while maximizing the net bit rate. Rather than enforcing cumulative budget constraints, we treat safety requirements as instantaneous operational limits and drive expected violation magnitudes toward zero via adaptive Lagrange multipliers.

Lagrangian relaxation. To handle the constraints, we adopt Lagrangian relaxation with adaptive dual variables. The resulting reward function is:

$$R_t = \frac{\bar{B}_r(t)}{B_{\max}} - \lambda_E \left[\frac{E_t - \tau_E}{\tau_E} \right]_+ - \lambda_B \left[\frac{\tau_B - b_t^{\min}}{\tau_B} \right]_+ \quad (6)$$

where $\lambda_E, \lambda_B \geq 0$ are Lagrange multipliers. Unlike fixed-penalty methods that are sensitive to coefficient selection [20], we update them adaptively via PID control (Section V-C), ensuring constraint satisfaction without manual tuning.

Transition dynamics. The transition kernel $P(s_{t+1} | s_t, a_t)$ is unknown and stochastic, driven by miner mobility, channel fading, and battery discharge.

Discount factor. We use $\gamma = 0.99$ to emphasize long-horizon battery preservation while maintaining learning stability.

IV. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a realistic underground mine composed of multiple production sections arranged in a room-and-pillar layout [21]. The WSN consists of M fixed sensor nodes and N mobile miners forming a delay-tolerant network (DTN). Miners are indexed by $\mathcal{N} = \{n_1, \dots, n_N\}$ and sensors by $\mathcal{M} = \{m_1, \dots, m_M\}$. All wireless communication in RL-MINDS operates over the 2.4 GHz ISM band using Bluetooth radios, consistent with the DTN architecture in [1]. Communication continuity around tunnel junctions and sharp turns is supported through strategically placed relay or repeater nodes, as motivated by empirical studies of underground propagation and tunnel waveguide effects [22]–[24]. Prior deployments of Bluetooth- and ZigBee-based underground sensor networks further confirm that 2.4 GHz communication can be reliable along mine corridors with appropriate node placement and topology design [3], [22].

The deployment comprises four main components: battery-powered sensor nodes, base stations, miners’ portable devices, and a site-level local server. Our objective is to *develop a DRL-based framework that assigns sensor duty cycles* to maximize average net bit rate subject to an energy budget. The DRL agent is trained centrally on the local server and dispatches duty-cycle commands to sensors via the BSs. We summarize the system components below (see Fig. 1):

1. **Miners’ devices.** Mobile user devices (e.g., tablets or wearables) carried by miners that exchange critical information with sensor nodes, including proximity and location-tracking data used to capture miner mobility patterns. *In practice, these mobile devices also act as Delay/disruption-tolerant networking (DTN) carrier nodes that temporarily store and forward sensor data between disconnected clusters, enabling reliable delivery under intermittent underground connectivity [25].*
2. **Sensor nodes.** Resource-constrained edge devices (e.g., Raspberry Pi) mounted on mine pillars, each with a unique ID and limited battery capacity. Nodes monitor environmental variables such as temperature, humidity, pressure, and toxic-gas concentration, and they participate in local communications (e.g., using 2.4 GHz bluetooth radios) with miners’ devices, neighboring sensors, and nearby BSs. Location information exchange follows the model in [1].
3. **Base stations (BSs).** BSs act as gateways aggregating data from nearby sensors and forwarding it to the site-level server over wired optical-fiber links. In many underground deployments, BSs are interconnected via an optical-fiber ring topology for long-reach connectivity and electromagnetic interference (EMI) immunity [8]. In our model a subset of pillar-mounted nodes serve as BSs; we assume

BSs have stable power and ample computational resources (i.e., they are not resource-constrained).

4. **Local server.** A site-level server (e.g., in a control room or surface station) that collects aggregated data from BSs, trains the DRL model using recorded traces, and computes optimal duty-cycle assignments. The server sends lightweight runtime models or explicit duty-cycle commands to nearby BSs for low-latency dissemination to sensor nodes; sensors then apply the received duty-cycle values to determine their active/sleep schedules.

Net Bit Rate Model. For sensor m at time slot t , let ζ_t^m denotes the instantaneous channel power and let ω_t^m be the transmission energy allocated in that slot. The instantaneous net bit rate (expected number of correctly received bits per unit time) is given by

$$B_r^m(\zeta_t^m, \omega_t^m) = \begin{cases} \frac{\chi_m L_S}{T_p} (1 - P_e^m(\zeta_t^m, \omega_t^m))^{\chi_m L_S}, & \omega_t^m > 0, \\ 0, & \omega_t^m = 0, \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where χ_m denotes the modulation order in bits per symbol, L_S is the number of symbols per packet, and T_p is the packet duration. The term $P_e^m(\cdot)$ represents the bit error rate (BER), and $(1 - P_e^m)^{\chi_m L_S}$ corresponds to the probability of receiving an entire packet of $\chi_m L_S$ bits without error.

Let $E_b^m = \omega_t^m / N_b^m$ denote the energy per bit, where $N_b^m = R_b T_{\text{tx}}^m(t)$ is the number of transmitted bits in slot t , with R_b the bit rate and $T_{\text{tx}}^m(t)$ the active transmission duration determined by the duty cycle. The resulting energy-per-bit to noise-density ratio is $\frac{E_b}{N_0} = \frac{E_b^m R_b}{N_0}$, where h_t^m is the channel gain and N_0 is the noise power spectral density. For Gaussian Frequency Shift Keying (GFSK) modulation with noncoherent detection [26], the BER is approximated as

$$P_e^m \approx \frac{1}{2} \exp\left(-\frac{E_b/N_0}{2}\right). \quad (8)$$

Energy Consumption Model. Let e_t^m denote the energy consumed by sensor m during slot t , and let $E_t = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} e_t^m$ represents the total network energy expenditure per slot. We adopt the per-slot energy consumption and battery dynamics model in [10], which accounts for transmit, receive, and idle costs as well as distance-dependent amplification. The DRL agent observes remaining battery levels and assigns duty cycles while enforcing a strict energy budget.

Underground Wireless Channel Model. To capture 2.4 GHz wireless propagation in underground mine corridors, we employ the log-distance path loss model validated through extensive experimental measurements in operational mines [27]:

$$PL(d) = PL(d_0) + 10n \log_{10}\left(\frac{d}{d_0}\right) + X_\sigma + L_{\text{add}}, \quad (9)$$

where $PL(d_0) = 40$ dB is the reference path loss at $d_0 = 1$ m, corresponding to free-space propagation at 2.4 GHz. The path-loss exponent is set to $n = 2.16$, consistent with CANMET underground measurements under mixed LOS and junction conditions [22]. Shadow fading is modeled as $X_\sigma \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$

Fig. 1. **RL-MINDS System Model.** *Left:* A delay-tolerant (DTN) segment where miners’ mobile devices opportunistically relay data among pillar-mounted Raspberry Pi sensor units (as part of WSN) in deep tunnels, maintaining connectivity under intermittent wireless coverage. Each sensor integrates environmental modules (CO₂, CH₄, temperature, and humidity) to broadcast real-time safety and mobility data. *Right:* System-level view of the RL-MINDS framework, where pillar sensors form a WSN connected to base stations via optical-fiber backhaul. The RL-MINDS agent, trained on a local surface server, continuously infers duty-cycle assignments for all sensors—adapting activation rates based on miner density, channel conditions, and battery status—to ensure reliable and energy-efficient underground monitoring.

with $\sigma = 6$ dB [22]. Additional scenario-dependent losses include $L_{\text{Junc}} \approx 8$ dB at tunnel junctions [28] and $L_{\text{Moist}} \approx 3$ dB due to surface moisture. The received power at distance d is

$$P_r(d) = P_t + G_t + G_r - PL(d), \quad (10)$$

where $P_t = 20$ dBm represents Class 1 Bluetooth transmission power (100 mW), and $G_t = G_r = 0$ dBi are the antenna gains.

All parameters are measured or estimated at the local server and included in the DRL state. The agent then selects duty cycles a_t^m (or equivalently ω_t^m) for each sensor to maximize throughput under energy and battery constraints.

V. RL-MINDS FRAMEWORK

A practical controller for an underground sensor network cannot operate efficiently on raw observations. The per-sensor features arriving each slot are high-dimensional, correlated across neighboring sensors, and noisy under non-stationary channel conditions. Training a policy on this input directly is statistically inefficient and slow to converge. The RL-MINDS framework therefore introduces an encoder that produces a compact latent representation of the network state, and trains the PPO policy on that representation rather than on raw features. The encoder uses self-attention to capture long-range dependencies across sensors, since coordinated scheduling decisions depend on sensor interactions that a purely local encoder cannot represent. The encoder is implemented as an attention-augmented variational autoencoder (Attention-VAE), and the overall pipeline is illustrated in Fig. 2. Below, we detail each stage of the framework’s operation.

Stage 1: Sensing and Aggregation. At time t , each sensor reports local features (battery level, miner load, received-signal/channel metric, gravity flag) to its serving BS. BSs stack features from their associated sensors and forward submatrices to the local server, which concatenates them into the global observation matrix $\mathbf{S}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times F}$. At the local server,

Fig. 2. Illustration of the agent–environment interaction underlying the proposed RL-MINDS framework.

constraint-aware margin features (energy and battery margins) are computed from system-level statistics and appended to each sensor’s feature vector before encoding. During training, trajectories are collected online from the simulator under the current system-level policy.

To make the convolution layers effective, we apply a fixed permutation of sensor indices so that sensors that are physically close in the mine are also adjacent in the input sequence. This way, local convolution filters capture correlations among nearby sensors rather than across arbitrary index orderings.

Stage 2: Latent Encoding. The encoder $f_{\text{enc}}(\cdot; \phi)$ at the local server maps each sensor’s augmented feature vector (raw measurements together with constraint-aware margin signals) into a higher-dimensional embedding via stacked convolutions, and then applies multi-head self-attention *across all sensors*.

This allows each sensor representation to attend to all others, capturing both local correlations and global dependencies before producing a Gaussian latent z_t that compactly summarizes the global system state while keeping safety-critical structure.

Stage 3: Policy Inference & Duty-cycle Assignment. The PPO actor π_θ takes input z_t and outputs a duty-cycle assignment $\mathbf{a}_t = [a_t^{(1)}, \dots, a_t^{(M)}]$, where each element lies in $[0, 0.95]$. The local server sends the corresponding duty-cycle command for each sensor back to its BS, which applies the schedule during the next slot.

Stage 4: Environment Transition. Once the agent selects action \mathbf{a}_t , it receives a reward \mathbf{R}_t as defined in Eq. (6). The environment transitions to the next state \mathbf{S}_{t+1} .

Stage 5: Training time VAE Update. The encoder–decoder parameters (ϕ, ψ) are updated every $k=4$ environment steps using the VAE loss in Eq. (11). This frequent but lightweight update allows the latent space to track slow drifts in miner distribution or channel conditions without destabilizing the PPO optimization, which updates on longer T -step trajectories.

Stage 6: PPO Policy Update. After T interactions, trajectories are used to compute advantages \hat{A}_t via Generalized Advantage Estimation (GAE)– λ , and to optimize the clipped surrogate objective $L^{\text{CLIP}}(\theta)$ and value loss $L_V(\mu)$.

A. State Representation via Attention-VAE

RL-MINDS employs an *Attention-VAE* to adaptively emphasize structurally critical sensors and to produce a compact, policy-relevant latent state. Local convolutional filters capture short-range correlations (e.g., neighbouring sensors that experience similar fading or battery decay) but typically fail to model long-range dependencies such as congestion at distant gravity points. Multi-head self-attention remedies this limitation by allowing each sensor representation to attend to all other sensors, thereby learning global interactions that are essential for coordinated, system-level control [29]. Concretely, the Attention-VAE combines convolutional feature extractors (to encode local spatial patterns) with a multi-head self-attention module (to capture global, pairwise dependencies across the M sensors).

The Attention-VAE produces a *probabilistic* latent z_t with two important properties: (i) **compression** — an $M \times F$ observation is mapped to a low-dimensional latent $z_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ with $d \ll MF$; and (ii) **denoising** — the reconstruction loss suppresses transient measurement noise from dynamic wireless channels. These properties ensure z_t preserves safety-critical structure rather than acting as an uninformed dimensionality reduction.

Unlike vision VAEs that are often trained offline and then frozen, RL-MINDS trains the encoder *jointly with* the policy to *avoid representation mismatch* as miner mobility and channel statistics drift. To further bias the latent toward features the controller actually uses, we add two lightweight auxiliary-prediction terms to the encoder loss. Let \mathcal{L}_{rec} denotes the reconstruction loss and $\text{KL}(\cdot \|\cdot)$ the usual VAE regularizer;

then the encoder objective is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VAE}} = \lambda_{\text{rec}} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}}] + \beta \text{KL}(q_\phi(z | s) \| p(z)) + \lambda_V \mathcal{L}_V(z) + \lambda_C \mathcal{L}_C(z) \quad (11)$$

where $\mathcal{L}_V(z)$ is a value-prediction auxiliary loss that trains a lightweight head to predict expected return from the latent, and $\mathcal{L}_C(z)$ is a constraint-prediction auxiliary loss that trains a second head to predict whether the energy and battery constraints will be violated. Both auxiliary heads operate on a partially detached latent z_{blend} that allows gradients to flow back into the encoder, biasing z toward retaining information predictive of return and constraint satisfaction. The weights $(\lambda_{\text{rec}}, \beta, \lambda_V, \lambda_C)$ control the relative contribution of each term and are specified in Table I. From a system-level standpoint, the latent embedding serves as a compact *mine state descriptor* summarizing energy distribution, connectivity, and miners’ mobility-induced dynamics across all sensors. By operating on this shared latent rather than independent node states, RL-MINDS coordinates duty-cycles globally, allowing energy conservation and communication reliability to emerge from collective behavior. Finally, multi-head attention adds modest computational overhead (roughly $O(M^2)$ pairwise interactions per attention layer) but yields significantly richer representations for system-level control; our simulations quantify the resulting gains in convergence speed and control performance.

Architectural overview. Let $\mathbf{S}_t \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times F}$ be the per-slot stacked observation (battery b_t^m , channel power ζ_t^m , miners-in-range k_t^m , gravity flag g^m , and constraint-aware margins μ_E^m, μ_B^m). We apply a fixed permutation of rows so physically proximate sensors are adjacent. The encoder first maps the 1D sequence of M sensors with three stacked 1D convolutions ($C=6$ input channels, width $W=64$, kernel 3) to capture local spatial correlations, then applies *multi-head self-attention* (4 heads) *across sensors* to model global dependencies (e.g., distant gravity points).

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V, \quad (12)$$

$$Q = HW_Q, \quad K = HW_K, \quad V = HW_V.$$

where H denotes the feature sequence from the convolutional stack and W_Q, W_K, W_V are the learned projection matrices for queries, keys, and values, respectively. The scaled dot-product attention allows each sensor embedding to aggregate information from all others, weighted by learned relevance. The resulting representation is flattened and mapped to a Gaussian latent $z_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_t, \text{diag}(\sigma_t^2))$ with $d = M$ (we set $d=100$ in our experiments). The decoder mirrors this structure (linear \rightarrow MHSA \rightarrow 1D convolutions) to reconstruct \mathbf{S}_t .

B. Proximal Policy Optimization on the Latent Space

Given the compact latent state z_t produced by the Attention-VAE, the actor outputs a joint duty-cycle action for the M sensors $\mathbf{a}_t = (a_t^1, \dots, a_t^M)$, $a_t^m \in [0, 0.95]$. We train the policy using the clipped PPO objective. Define the probability ratio:

$$\rho_t(\theta) = \frac{\pi_\theta(\mathbf{a}_t | z_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(\mathbf{a}_t | z_t)}, \quad (13)$$

and compute advantages with GAE:

$$\begin{aligned}\delta_t &= R_t + \gamma V_\mu(z_{t+1}) - V_\mu(z_t), \\ \hat{A}_t &= \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} (\gamma\lambda)^l \delta_{t+l},\end{aligned}\quad (14)$$

where γ is the discount factor. The GAE- λ estimator balances bias and variance in the computed advantage values. The clipped surrogate objective for the policy is

$$L^{\text{CLIP}}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_t \left[\min \left(\rho_t(\theta) \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(\rho_t(\theta), 1-\varepsilon, 1+\varepsilon) \hat{A}_t \right) \right], \quad (15)$$

where ε is the clipping parameter. The value-function is learned by minimizing the squared temporal-difference error:

$$L_V(\mu) = \mathbb{E}_t \left[(R_t + \gamma V_\mu(z_{t+1}) - V_\mu(z_t))^2 \right]. \quad (16)$$

Training proceeds in epochs: after collecting T environment interactions (rollouts), we perform E epochs of stochastic optimization over mini-batches sampled from the experience buffer. The parameter updates are

$$\begin{aligned}\theta &\leftarrow \theta + \alpha_\theta \nabla_\theta L^{\text{CLIP}}(\theta), \\ \mu &\leftarrow \mu - \alpha_\mu \nabla_\mu L_V(\mu),\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

where α_θ and α_μ are the policy and value learning rates, respectively. In practice, we apply entropy regularization to the policy objective and gradient clipping to stabilize learning.

C. Constraint Handling via Lagrangian Relaxation

Standard RL maximizes cumulative reward without explicit constraint enforcement. To handle the energy and battery constraints in our CMDP formulation, we employ Lagrangian relaxation, converting the constrained optimization into an unconstrained problem. The Lagrangian is:

$$\mathcal{L}(\pi, \lambda) = J(\pi) - \lambda_E \mathbb{E}_\pi [C_E(s_t, a_t)] - \lambda_B \mathbb{E}_\pi [C_B(s_t)] \quad (18)$$

where $\lambda_E, \lambda_B \geq 0$ are Lagrange multipliers (dual variables). The policy (primal variable) is updated via PPO to maximize \mathcal{L} , while the multipliers (dual variables) are updated to enforce constraint satisfaction. Fixed penalty coefficients require problem-specific tuning and may need re-adjustment when operating conditions change [20]. We update the multipliers using a PID controller [30]:

$$\lambda_{k+1} = \max \left(0, K_P g_k + K_I \sum_{j \leq k} g_j + K_D (g_k - g_{k-1}) \right), \quad (19)$$

where $g_k = \mathbb{E}_{\pi_k} [C]$ is the observed average constraint violation over the most recent training window. The proportional term responds to the current violation, the integral term accumulates persistent errors, and the derivative term dampens oscillations. We adopt $K_P = 0.5$, $K_I = 0.01$, $K_D = 2.0$ following the tuning guidelines in [30]. The optimal policy of a constrained MDP can be characterized as a saddle point of the Lagrangian under standard regularity conditions [19], and PID-based dual updates have been shown empirically to

Algorithm 1: RL-MINDS Training Process

Input: Number of training episodes E , time-steps per episode T , learning rate α
Output: Trained policy π_θ , encoder f_{enc} , decoder f_{dec}

- 1 Initialize encoder $f_{\text{enc}}(\cdot; \theta_{\text{enc}})$ and decoder $f_{\text{dec}}(\cdot; \theta_{\text{dec}})$ with random weights
- 2 Initialize PPO policy π_θ and value function V_μ with random parameters
- 3 Initialize optimizer for encoder-decoder pair (VAE) with learning rate α
- 4 Initialize environment env and wrap it with VAE observation wrapper
- 5 **for** $e = 1$ to E **do**
- 6 Reset environment and obtain initial observation s_0
- 7 **for** $t = 1$ to T **do**
- 8 — **PPO Training Step** —
- 9 Use policy π_θ to sample action a_t from latent representation $z_t = f_{\text{enc}}(s_t)$
- 10 Execute a_t in the environment to obtain next state s_{t+1} and reward r_t
- 11 Store transition (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) in trajectory buffer
- 12 — **Online VAE Update** —
- 13 Flatten and normalize raw observation s_t into vector x_t
- 14 Encode: $(z_t, \mu_t, \log \sigma_t^2) \leftarrow f_{\text{enc}}(x_t)$
- 15 Decode: $\hat{x}_t \leftarrow f_{\text{dec}}(z_t)$
- 16 Compute reconstruction loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}} = \|x_t - \hat{x}_t\|^2$
- 17 Compute KL divergence $\mathcal{D}_{\text{KL}} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum (1 + \log \sigma_t^2 - \mu_t^2 - \exp(\log \sigma_t^2))$
- 18 Compute value-prediction loss $\mathcal{L}_V = \|V_\psi(z_t) - \hat{R}_t\|^2$
- 19 Compute constraint-prediction loss $\mathcal{L}_C = \text{BCE}(C_\psi(z_t), c_t)$, where BCE denotes binary cross-entropy
- 20 Total VAE loss: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{VAE}} = \lambda_{\text{rec}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{rec}} + \beta \mathcal{D}_{\text{KL}} + \lambda_V \mathcal{L}_V + \lambda_C \mathcal{L}_C$
- 21 Update $\theta_{\text{enc}}, \theta_{\text{dec}}$ via gradient descent on \mathcal{L}_{VAE}
- 22 — **PPO Policy Update** —
- 23 After T timesteps, compute advantage estimates \hat{A}_t and update PPO
- 24 Optimize policy using clipped objective: $L^{\text{CLIP}}(\theta)$
- 25 Optimize critic network using value loss $L_V(\mu)$
- 26 **return** $\pi_\theta, f_{\text{enc}}, f_{\text{dec}}$

reduce oscillation and improve responsiveness in deep RL benchmarks [30].

This formulation allows the multipliers to increase when constraints are violated and decrease when satisfied, adapting the penalty strength to the observed constraint gaps during training.

Algorithm 1 outlines the full RL-MINDS training process.

VI. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Experimental Setup

We consider a 3 km \times 3 km underground mine with a room-and-pillar tunnel layout. Each pillar hosts a battery-powered sensor node ($M = 100$ nodes total). Network traffic comprises periodic environmental telemetry, opportunistic data exchange with miners' devices, and per-slot uploads to the serving

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Hyperparameter	Symbol	Value
Total time steps	-	1.64M
Number of base stations	-	9
Mine area	-	3Km × 3Km
Learning rate	α	5×10^{-5}
Discount rate	γ	0.99
PPO Clip range	ϵ	0.2
Batch size	-	128
GAE parameter	λ	0.95
Number of Sensor nodes	-	100
Number of Miners	-	500
Broadcasting distance	-	100 m
Per-step total energy threshold	E_{thr}	2J
Battery safety threshold	b_{min}	25%
VAE En/Decoder Parameters		
Latent dimension	d	100
Convolution layers	-	3 with 3 kernel
Attention heads (MHSA)	-	4
Activation	-	ReLU
KL weight	β	1.0
Reconstruction weight	λ_{rec}	1.0
KL weight	β	0.01
Value-prediction weight	λ_V	0.3
Constraint-prediction weight	λ_C	0.3
Optimizer	-	Adam (10^{-4})
Training frequency	-	every 4 steps

BS. The bit error rate follows Eq. (7), and per-slot energy consumption follows the radio model, same as [10].

Miner Mobility Model. We generate realistic miner movement traces using the ONE Simulator [31], following the methodology established in prior underground mine DTN research [1]. The simulation spans an 8-hour shift with 500 miners and 100 static sensor nodes deployed at pillars. Miners are categorized into four types with role-specific movement parameters: (i) *production miners* (300), (ii) *supervisors* (50), (iii) *trolley operators* (100), and (iv) *maintenance crews* (50). Each type has distinct speed and pause-time distributions (5–15 minutes) reflecting realistic underground work patterns. Miners follow a shortest-path map-based movement model constrained to the tunnel network, selecting destinations based on role-specific waypoints and pausing upon arrival before proceeding.

Baselines. We compare RL-MINDS against five baselines: *three learning-based variants and two rule-based heuristics*. All methods operate on the same per-slot observation vector (battery level, channel power, miner load, gravity flag, energy margin, and battery margin), optimize the reward in Eq. (6), and share an identical training setup and compute budget (Table I). The baselines are described below:

A. Learning-based baselines:

1. *CNN+PPO*: This baseline follows the architecture in [6], which extends earlier PPO-based WSN control [32] by adding convolutional encoding of the $M \times F$ observation matrix. We compare against this improved variant rather

than vanilla PPO, as it represents the stronger, state-of-the-art version from the same research line. The actor outputs a continuous duty-cycle vector $\mathbf{a}_t \in [0, 0.95]^M$. This baseline represents the standard DRL-based resource-allocation paradigm applied to system-level WSN control.

2. *A2C (Advantage Actor-Critic)*: We replace the basic actor-critic algorithm in [9] with A2C, which reduces variance through advantage estimation. The $M \times F$ observation is encoded via shared fully connected layers, and the actor outputs continuous duty-cycle actions $\mathbf{a}_t \in [0, 0.95]^M$.
3. *LSTM+PPO*: We adapt the PPO-LSTM architecture from [10], originally designed for battery-level prediction, to our duty-cycle control task. The LSTM encodes temporal sequences of sensor observations, and the PPO actor outputs continuous duty-cycle actions $\mathbf{a}_t \in [0, 0.95]^M$. This baseline captures temporal correlations but lacks explicit mechanisms for cross-sensor spatial coordination.

B. Rule-based baselines (non-learning):

1. *Fixed Duty Cycle (FDC)*: A uniform (e.g. 50%) duty fraction is applied to all nodes regardless of local conditions. This static baseline represents legacy WSN deployments and provides a performance reference for non-adaptive scheduling.
2. *Traffic-Proportional Heuristic (TPH)*: Inspired by traffic-aware duty-cycle allocation schemes, this heuristic computes a per-node priority score combining normalized channel quality, traffic load (miners-in-range), and gravity-point status. The priority is mapped to a duty fraction in $[\delta_{\text{min}}, \delta_{\text{max}}]$. Unlike learning-based methods, TPH uses fixed weights and cannot adapt to constraint violations or temporal traffic patterns.

Environment. All simulations (RL-MINDS and baselines) are implemented in PyTorch 2.2 and STABLE-BASELINES3 2.3, using Python 3.10.12 and OpenAI Gym 0.25.2 (commonly used in WSN+RL literature). Training was performed on an NVIDIA Tesla K80 GPU (12 GB VRAM).

We train RL-MINDS for approximately 1.64M environment steps using PPO with 8 parallel environments. Unless otherwise stated, we use the Adam optimizer with linear learning-rate decay. Key PPO/VAE hyperparameters are summarized in Table I. All baselines follow the same training protocol and compute budget to ensure fair comparison.

Evaluation protocol. Learning methods are trained until convergence. A 200,000-step is implemented for the rule-based methods. Metrics reported use identical environment seeds, channel traces, and battery initializations across all methods.

B. Results and Discussion

Overall performance (Net Bit Rate). As shown in Fig. 3, RL-MINDS achieves a consistently higher average net bit rate than all baselines, yielding a 28% improvement over CNN+PPO at convergence. These gains arise from the attention-VAE encoder, which (i) *denoises channel fluctuations* via its reconstruction objective, and (ii) *captures cross-sensor dependencies* via multi-head self-attention, enabling

Fig. 3. Average net bit rate of RL-MINDS vs baselines.

Fig. 4. System-level average energy consumption of RL-MINDS and baselines under varying energy-budget thresholds.

coordinated duty-cycle assignment among spatially correlated sensors. Removing the attention module reduces throughput by about 7%, confirming its key role in system-level coordination. **Energy efficiency under budget constraints.** Fig. 4 reports system-level energy consumption under the 2.0 J budget. RL-MINDS utilizes 95% of the available energy (1.9 J) while exhibiting only 1.4% energy-constraint violations at convergence (see Fig. 5). In contrast, CNN+PPO and LSTM+PPO underutilize the budget (87%) yet incur higher violation rates (3.8% and 4.3%, respectively), reflecting less precise constraint control. A2C is overly conservative, consuming only 50% of the budget and showing unstable behavior, thereby sacrificing throughput to avoid violations. All learning-based methods converge to near-zero battery violations (see Fig. 6), indicating that the PID-controlled Lagrangian effectively enforces the battery threshold across architectures.

Constraint adaptation dynamics. Fig. 7 illustrates how the

Fig. 5. Energy-constraint violations of RL-MINDS vs baselines.

Fig. 6. Battery Constraint Violations of RL-MINDS vs baselines.

Fig. 7. Constraint adaptation dynamics during early training (rollouts 0–9): (a) battery violation rate, (b) Lagrangian multiplier λ_B , (c) battery safety margin, and (d) policy response.

PID-Lagrangian mechanism enforces constraints during training, using the battery constraint as a representative example (rollouts 0–9). During initial exploration, battery violations increase as the policy has not yet adapted to the constraint boundary. In response, the PID-controlled dual update raises λ_B (Fig. 7 b), increasing the penalty on constraint-violating actions. Notably, the minimum battery level begins recovering by rollout 4–5 (Fig. 7 c) before the mean duty cycle shows

Fig. 8. Average reward of RL-MINDS vs baselines.

TABLE II
RULE-BASED COMPARISON OF RL-MINDS AND BASELINES.

Method	NBR (bps)	Energy Util.	B_viol (%)
FDC (50%)	40,253	94.1%	86.2
TPH	16,220	47.5%	87.4
RL-MINDS	59,000	95.0%	≈ 0

substantial reduction (Fig. 7 d). This indicates that the policy first learns to selectively protect at-risk sensors—reducing duty cycles for nodes approaching the battery threshold while maintaining throughput elsewhere—rather than uniformly lowering all duty cycles. The mean duty cycle decline in later rollouts (6–8) reflects further policy refinement as the system-level controller optimizes the throughput-constraint trade-off. Fig. 7 c reports both the true per-rollout minimum battery level and the averaged statistic used by the controller, confirming that λ_B responds to the correct constraint signal. These results show that RL-MINDS adaptively enforces battery constraints via learned dual variables, achieving differentiated per-sensor control without manual tuning penalty tuning.

Learning stability and final return. Fig. 8 shows the average-return curves, where RL-MINDS converges faster and attains a higher asymptotic return (58) than baselines. RL-MINDS (No Attention) converges similarly fast but plateaus lower (54), while CNN+PPO and LSTM+PPO improve more gradually, reaching 44 and 40, respectively. A2C exhibits high variance and plateaus at 27, reflecting its unstable energy allocation. The faster convergence of both RL-MINDS variants indicates that the VAE’s compact latent state accelerates policy learning. **Rule-based baselines (FDC vs. TPH).** Table II summarizes the performance of rule-based methods. The Fixed Duty Cycle (FDC) baseline applies a uniform 50% duty fraction to all sensors, achieving 40,253 bps throughput by utilizing 94% of the available energy budget. However, FDC cannot adapt to constraint boundaries: sensors continue transmitting at full capacity, resulting in 86.2% battery violation rate.

The Traffic-Proportional Heuristic (TPH) attempts to improve upon FDC by allocating higher duty cycles to sensors with better channel conditions and higher traffic loads. Counterintuitively, TPH achieves significantly *worse* throughput (16,220 bps, a 60% reduction) while providing no meaningful improvement in battery violations (87.4%). The conservative allocation protects sensors that face no depletion risk while failing to address the true bottleneck.

These results highlight two failure modes of rule-based scheduling: (i) static allocation (FDC) cannot react to violations, and (ii) proportional heuristics (TPH) may severely under-utilize resources under skewed traffic. RL-MINDS overcomes both via PID-controlled Lagrangian adaptation, selectively protecting at-risk sensors while sustaining high network throughput.

Failure-tolerance evaluation. A practical concern in underground deployments is the policy’s resilience to sensor failures, which can arise from battery depletion, hardware

TABLE III
FAILURE TOLERANCE OF RL-MINDS UNDER VARYING SENSOR FAILURE RATES (f SENSORS FAILED OUT OF 100). VALUES ARE MEAN \pm STANDARD DEVIATION ACROSS 15 EPISODES.

f	NBR _{live} (bps)	NBR _{sys} (bps)	Energy (J)
0	58,900 \pm 0	58,900 \pm 0	1.90 \pm 0.00
10	59,111 \pm 1,766	53,200 \pm 1,590	1.72 \pm 0.05
20	59,217 \pm 2,560	47,373 \pm 2,048	1.53 \pm 0.06
30	58,086 \pm 3,023	40,660 \pm 2,116	1.31 \pm 0.07

faults, dust ingress, and equipment damage. We evaluate RL-MINDS under uniform random sensor failure: at the start of each evaluation episode, f sensors are randomly selected and marked as failed for the entire episode. Failed sensors contribute zero throughput and zero energy, while the remaining sensors operate under the trained policy. We vary $f \in \{0, 10, 20, 30\}$ corresponding to 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30% sensor failure, with 15 independent episodes per failure level (1,000 environment steps each).

Table III reports two throughput conventions: NBR_{live}, the mean net bit rate averaged over surviving sensors only, and NBR_{sys}, the total network net bit rate divided by the deployed sensor count. The former measures per-sensor service quality, while the latter captures aggregate system performance. System-level throughput NBR_{sys} degrades approximately linearly with the failure count, from 58,900 bps at $f = 0$ to 40,660 bps at $f = 30$ (a 31% reduction at 30% sensor failure). Per-surviving-sensor throughput NBR_{live} remains within $\pm 2\%$ of the no-failure value across all failure levels. Energy consumption decreases with f , from 1.90 J/step at $f = 0$ to 1.31 J/step at $f = 30$, remaining below the 2.0 J threshold across all failure regimes. The increasing standard deviation in NBR_{sys} with f (from 1,590 to 2,116 bps) reflects variance over which specific sensors are masked in each random realization.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented RL-MINDS, a *system-level duty-cycle* controller for underground wireless sensing that integrates an attention-enhanced variational autoencoder with a PPO agent. We formulated duty-cycle assignment as a CMDP that explicitly models miner density (as miners move through tunnels), underground channel quality, battery state, gravity-point indicators, and addressed the resulting large, correlated observation space through latent-state learning. The learned policy operates on a compact representation, enabling coordinated, real-time duty-cycle adjustment across multiple sensors under tight energy constraints. Comprehensive simulations demonstrate that RL-MINDS outperforms both learning-based (CNN+PPO, A2C, and LSTM+PPO) and rule-based baselines: it achieves higher average net bit rate, better adherence to per-slot energy budgets, fewer constraint violations. These improvements stem from (i) representation learning that denoises volatile underground channels (ii) adaptive constraint handling mechanism and (iii) a unified, system-level policy that enhances cross-sensor

coordination, leading to higher throughput at comparable energy consumption and lower rates of battery depletion.

In future work, we will implement this application as a prototype system and conduct a real-world performance evaluation in an underground mining environment at the experimental mine facility at Missouri S&T.

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